

Systematic Review Protocol

This review protocol has been conducted following the preferred PRISMA-P reporting items of Shamseer et al. (2015) when applicable to a nonclinical systematic review (basic research).

PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols) 2015 checklist: recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol*

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION		
Title:		
Identification	1a	<i>Streptomyces</i> as potential synthetic polymer degraders: A Systematic Review
Update	1b	N/A
Registration	2	There is no direct outcome relevance to human health, and therefore this review does not meet the scope of the PROSPERO registrations and is not registered.
Authors:		
Contact	3a	Corresponding author: Luis Eduardo Díaz Barrera; luis.diaz1@unisabana.edu.co Other authors: Jeysson Sánchez-Suárez; Maria F. Rodríguez-Fonseca Author affiliations: Universidad de La Sabana, Chía 250001, Colombia
Contributions	3b	Conceptualization, M. F. R.-F., L. E. D.-B., and J. S.-S.; methodology, M. F R-F, and J. S-S.; software, M.F.R-F, and J.S-S.; validation, M. F. R-F, L. E. D-B, J. S-S; formal analysis, M.F. R-F.; investigation, M.F. R-F.; data curation, M. F. R-F, L. E. D-B, and J. S-S.; supervision, L. E. D-B. L.E.D.B is guarantor of the review All authors have read and agreed to the systematic review protocol.
Amendments	4	If this protocol has to be modified, the date of each modification shall be indicated, and the change shall be described with due justification in this section.
Support:		
Sources	5a	This research was funded by Universidad Nacional Abierta y a Distancia (UNAD), project number PS072020 and by Universidad de La Sabana, project number ING-204-2018.
Sponsor	5b	Universidad de La Sabana, Universidad Nacional Abierta y a Distancia

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item
Role of sponsor or funder	5c	The funders have had no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.
INTRODUCTION		
Rationale	6	Microorganisms have shown great potential in the degradation of complex polymers, including synthetic plastics. This has resulted in increased research into their use as biodegraders for bioremediation of plastic-contaminated environments. Among the various microorganism options, there are reports of promising potential in strains of the genus <i>Streptomyces</i> . There are no systematic reviews collecting and analyzing the information available in the literature on synthetic plastic degrading streptomycetes.
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to participants, interventions, comparators, and outcomes (PICO)
METHODS		
Eligibility criteria	8	<p>Studies will be selected according to the criteria outlined below:</p> <p><i>Study designs:</i> Peer-reviewed original articles in scholarly journals are included; narrative and systematic reviews, book chapters, reports, and grey literature overall are excluded.</p> <p><i>Problem:</i> <i>Streptomyces</i> strains evaluated on their potential for biodegradation of synthetic plastics.</p> <p><i>Interventions:</i> All studies will be included regardless of the type of intervention.</p> <p><i>Comparators:</i> Studies with any types of comparators or control types will be included.</p> <p><i>Outcomes:</i> Outcomes will be collected, synthesized, analysed and reported descriptively.</p> <p><i>Time:</i> The search will be without time restriction.</p> <p><i>Language:</i> Articles written in the English language will be included.</p>
Information sources	9	Literature search strategies will be developed using synonyms and related terms in generic and technical where applicable. The literature search will be performed in the databases: Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed and the Google Scholar search engine.
Search strategy	10	<p><i>Scopus:</i> TITLE-ABS-KEY (streptomyces AND (plastic OR polymer OR polyethylene OR polystyrene OR polypropylene OR polyurethane OR "polyethylene terephthalate" OR "polyvinyl chloride") AND (degradation OR biodegradation))</p> <p><i>Web of Science/PubMed:</i> (streptomyces AND (plastic OR polymer OR polyeth-ylene OR polystyrene OR polypropylene</p>

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item
		OR polyurethane OR "polyethylene terephthalate" OR "polyvinyl chloride") AND (degradation OR biodegradation)) <i>Google Scholar:</i> streptomyces plastic polymer polyethylene polystyrene poly-propylene polyurethane "polyethylene terephthalate" "polyvinyl chloride" degradation biodegradation
Study records:		
Data management	11a	Literature search results will be uploaded to Rayyan QCRI tool Software, an Internet based software program that facilitates collaboration among reviewers during the study selection process. The team will screen articles based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Prior to the formal screening process, a calibration exercise will be undertaken to pilot and refine the screening process. Further, we will provide training to new members of the review team not familiar with the Rayyan QCRI tool Software and the content area prior to the start of the review.
Selection process	11b	To avoid bias in article selection, the selection process was performed separately in a blinded manner by each of the three researchers; thus, each researcher assessed the titles and abstracts individually using the Rayyan QCRI tool.
Data collection process	11c	An acquisition form will be designed to ensure careful data collection. The form will be designed by one researcher and evaluated by another to avoid collection bias. Once the final version of the form will be determined, it will be used for data collection of the included articles after screening process. Data will be tabulated using the form by one researcher and validated by a second researcher.
Data items	12	Country of sample collection, Isolation source, Name of macroorganism source, Streptomyces species ID name, Access code collection, Identification method, Culture type, Culture medium name, Methodology involved in the polymer degradation assay, Results of the degradation assay, Comments and other notes.
Outcomes and prioritization	13	Primary outcomes will be the percentage of degradation of the plastic polymer. Any additional outcomes related to the measurement of the degree of polymer degradation will be considered.
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	N/A
Data synthesis	15a	If the studies are sufficiently homogeneous in terms of design and comparator, we will perform meta-analysis, otherwise, we will proceed to statistically describe the results found. If the latter possibility does not exist, we will proceed to perform a qualitative synthesis of the data found.
	15b	A systematic narrative synthesis will be provided with the information presented in the text and tables to summarize and explain the characteristics and results of the included studies. The narrative synthesis will explore the relationship and findings both within and between the included studies.
	15c	N/A
	15d	N/A
Meta-bias(es)	16	N/A
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	N/A

*** It is strongly recommended that this checklist be read in conjunction with the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration (cite when available) for important clarification on the items. Amendments to a review protocol should be tracked and dated. The copyright for PRISMA-P (including checklist) is held by the PRISMA-P Group and is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Licence 4.0.**

From: Shamseer L, Moher D, Clarke M, Ghersi D, Liberati A, Petticrew M, Shekelle P, Stewart L, PRISMA-P Group. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. BMJ. 2015 Jan 2;349(jan02 1):g7647.